

In America, women are granted liberties such as the right to vote, to own property, to remain unmarried, and to pursue education, among other basic societal needs. Now that women have been granted these freedoms after thousands of years of struggle, feminism as a whole is seen by many—primarily men—as a past issue. This stance is proven through the language that my modern generation of men uses when speaking on the topic of feminism and the way in which they refer to a woman’s accomplishments. Because they themselves don’t believe they are misogynistic in the way that people 50 to 5,000 years ago were misogynistic, they feel free to refer to and think about women using language that is systematically harmful without ever realizing it. They aren’t able to realize the error of their ways and the impact of their negligence because they’ve never found themselves in situations where they’d be called out by their male peers for perhaps saying something offensive, out of touch, or stereotypical. The way in which young men view the issue of feminism in the past tense rather than the present tense contributes to a misuse of language regarding women, skepticism toward women’s accomplishments and the methods used to achieve them, and even self-doubt among women of their own potential.

This past summer, I was freshly graduated from high school and volunteering in different parts of a hospital with my younger brother. I became acquainted with this one guy, Anthony, about four years older than me, through our shared volunteer work. I remember one night he came up to my younger brother and me and started talking about a girl who had rejected him in another wing of the hospital. My brother and I were sympathetic at first, but his attitude began to shift from solemn to resentful as he continued discussing the event. It escalated to the point where he was insulting the girl’s grades, her hospital work, and her friends, eventually calling both her and her friends, “...just a bunch of c*nts.” I cut him off at that point, as I didn’t want this to get any worse than it already was—especially around my younger brother—and told him,

“Alright man, chill out.” He snapped back, “We’re all guys here anyway. Lay off.” That was my last impression of him as he never signed up to volunteer again in the same group as my brother and me.

This was the first of many cases in which I would directly see the difference between how men act around women versus how they may actually view women. Two specifically sickening aspects of this experience was the way Anthony was so quick to insult her intelligence after the rejection and the way his derogatory language wasn’t directed just as an insult to her, but to her friends and women as a whole. These aspects are especially upsetting, knowing that he doesn’t realize he wasn’t just being rude to this girl, he was being rude while also contributing to systemic misogyny. While he was nitpicking this girl’s work out of frustration over his rejection, I couldn’t help but question whether he’d ever considered criticizing me and my work—his male peer—in this manner, or if he ever considered any of his male peers’ work as critically as he clearly considered hers. This question struck me especially as a transgender male who had been socialized as a girl until the age of 14, had experienced the absurd criticisms that come with being perceived as female, and eventually came to understand the undeniable privilege that comes with being perceived as male. Questioning his criticisms with my own background in mind made me realize just how easily a woman’s competence can be dismissed from a cisgender male perspective.

While it’s no secret that women’s accomplishments have historically been looked at with a closer, more critical lens than those of men, the negative manifestation of this bias still persists today and is reflected through modern language. What I mean by this is that the language used to question women’s work is language that can be considered inherently undermining. In Sherry Turkle’s *The Triumph of Tinkering*, she explains this idea in a scientific context as she writes,

“Our culture tends to equate the word ‘soft’ with unscientific and undisciplined as well as with the feminine and with a lack of power” (Turkle 572). Turkle takes the meaning of just one word associated with femininity and explains the common viewpoint around it and how its use in a critical context negatively impacts the perspectives on women’s work. She connects the use of this word to a power dynamic in order to further exemplify the way in which it actively puts women down systematically. In the scientific context from which Turkle is speaking, this differentiation in language between men and women is especially important, as women have been consistently underrepresented in scientific study. Turkle argues that there is an unfair connection between the words “soft,” “femininity,” and “unscientific” (Turkle 572), and while I don’t predict this connection will change anytime soon, it’s worth noting, as language use similar to this is present everywhere and contributes to the invalidation of female achievement.

Not only are the actual accomplishments that women make doubted in almost every field, but the methods women use to produce these accomplishments are doubted as well. Women are brought up to think and work in a way that is more considerate of the audience digesting their work because of the scrutiny that they know it will receive—Turkle refers to this way of thinking as “the soft approach” (Turkle 572). This upbringing lends itself to different ways of thinking and problem-solving between men and women. Men aren’t taught to expect the same criticism of their work that women are, and because of that, one could argue that their process of thinking tends to be more streamlined than a woman’s. This is an argument made by individuals attempting to find holes in women’s approaches to work in order to find invalidity in it. Anthony had tried to use this argument as he was expressing frustration toward the girl who rejected him, pointing out how she completed her work differently than he would, as a jab at her overall intelligence. This common misogynistic argument is hypocritical, as it criticizes the effectiveness

of “the soft approach” yet doesn’t recognize that the reason women are raised to think with this “soft approach” is because they’re trying to avoid this exact kind of criticism. Ultimately, this argument is ineffective not just because it’s hypocritical, but because it cannot prove that the work women produce through this more considerate thinking method, or “soft approach,” is less valuable than that of a man. The way in which both minds, male and female, work toward and achieve the same goal remains the same, no matter the process behind it. Even though the girl who rejected Anthony was supposedly completing her work in a different manner than he was, the results of both their work would’ve been exactly the same, and so his insult toward her overall intelligence is invalid.

As a result of the male doubt placed onto women’s accomplishments, a sense of insecurity and a need to change their methods for success are shared amongst certain women. Constantly having to prove worth in something that is pushed aside again and again by men who don’t care to see its potential causes these women to shift their approach, and consequently causes them to lose parts of what made their results originally impactful. This is especially the case in male-dominated fields like computer science, engineering, or finance, where women often train themselves to think like a man might in order to try to prove the validity of their work. This shift in the way certain women feel that they need to think causes them to lose individuality in their work as they try to make it more palatable to the male gaze. Turkle reflects on this shift in thinking in a computational field, stating, “Their [women’s] style of thinking would have them get close to the computational objects, but the closer they got, the more anxious they felt” (Turkle 578). This explains how, even if women get closer to success by attempting to adapt to the male standard, there is a sense of anxiousness created because of their loss of their original thought processes. This idea is reflected in another quote from Turkle, in which she states,

“Women have too often been faced with the choice—not necessarily conscious—of putting themselves at odds with the cultural meaning of being a scientist or with the cultural construction of being a woman” (Turkle 578). This describes the internal battle that certain women experience between the way of thinking they were raised to use and the way of thinking that they attempt to adopt in order for the men in the male-dominated field they work in to better understand their contributions. I, too, understand this sense of insecurity that comes from a shift in thinking as someone who has been consistently trying to find inclusion in male spaces because of my transition. Going from someone who primarily surrounded myself with female friends who had understood me since my childhood, to adapting to male friend groups as I got older, I lost a sense of familiarity. The individual I was around my female friends was vastly different from the one I found myself becoming around my male friends, and over time, I realized I had lost a version of myself along the way. I had been so focused on fighting so desperately to feel included and valid in a male-dominated space that I didn’t understand what I was giving up. This ties back to how comfortable Anthony was saying all those disgusting things about the girl who rejected him—because I know he would never have said those things around the version of me that hadn’t been socialized as male.

The sense of doubt men exhibit toward women’s achievements, how it reflects on the methods women use to reach those achievements, and the effects of how women have found themselves adapting to this doubt, is an ongoing issue. While the advancements that women as a whole have made in just the past 100 years are significant, aspects of misogyny still linger in the use of language and attitudes toward them. Turkle offers an understanding of these aspects, but what I find especially important about her writing is how it demonstrates the equality between men and women in fields where it isn’t always so obvious. The education Turkle provides is a

type of social education that gives perspective to be used in one's everyday life to implement change in the treatment of women's ideas. Understanding the ways in which women are targeted and doubted in workplaces, educational settings, and male-dominated environments in general is something I feel everyone can benefit from being more educated about.